

MEDICAL SCIENCES

GAMA VARIANT COVID 19 AND ILIAC AORTA ISCHEMIA

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Abstract

The objective of the present study is to report acute critical aortoiliac ischemia in Gama variant. We report the case of a 57-year-old patient with a history of Gama variant (COVID-19) and she was admitted to the emergency room with a report of sudden pain in the left lower limb that started 8 hours ago, associated with paresthesia and cyanosis of the left foot. Diagnosis of acute arterial occlusion of the left lower limb with Rutherford classification 2A. She underwent emergency Duplex Scan of the left lower limb, with a finding of high resistance flow in the proximal segment of the left common iliac and occlusion of the distal segment of the common iliac artery, external iliac artery, and common femoral artery, with an image suggestive of the thrombosis. The patient underwent urgent arterial embolectomy of the left lower limb 12 hours after the onset of symptoms. At the end of the procedure, reestablishment of arterial flow was evidenced. He is discharged 96 hours after admission, suspended low molecular weight heparin (LMWH) and prescribed warfarin sodium for daily use. Patient currently under outpatient follow-up for INR control.

Keywords: Gama variant, Iliac aorta, ischemia, treatment, COVID-19

Introduction

Coronavirus-2019 disease (COVID-19) predisposes to thrombosis whose underlying mechanisms are still not fully understood, where the balance between pro-coagulating factors and natural coagulation inhibitors in the critical patient with COVID-19 is fundamental in preventing and treatment of complications.¹

In literature some studies confirms that critically ill patients with coronavirus can develop arterial and deep vein thrombosis with a high risk of mortality. Early and adequate management can improve overall survival, especially in patients aged 60 years or younger.²⁻⁴

Other study recent in patients with coronavirus-19 show that D-dimer levels are elevated, and the test appears to be reliable in screening for deep vein thrombosis (DVT) at or above 3000 ng/mL (more than 13 times the normal range). Although we may think that these isolated criteria can often be limiting in predicting DVT.⁵

Anticoagulation is one of the approaches associated with reducing mortality. However, the dosage and what is the best option needs to be analyzed, One study evaluating the intermediate dosage had 2.5% major bleeding events in the intermediate dose group with 1.07% fatal events and 4 (1.4%) major bleeding events in the prophylactic standard dose group with no mortal-

ity.⁶ Study of review show it is unclear about anticoagulants-dose in patients with COVID-19, many controversies in results and different conditions.⁷

Genome sequencing of viruses sampled in Manaus between November 2020 and January 2021 revealed the emergence and circulation of a worrying new variant of SARS-CoV-2. The P.1 strain acquired 17 mutations, including a trio in the spike protein (K417T, E484K and N501Y) associated with increased binding to the human ACE2 receptor (angiotensin-converting enzyme 2).⁸ The aim of the present study is to report a case of thrombosis of tibial arteries 20 days after hospital discharge from the Gama variant and analyze the approach taken.

Case report

We report the case of a 57-year-old patient with a history of variant Gama infection. She was admitted to the emergency room with a report of sudden pain in the left lower limb that started 8 hours ago, associated with paresthesia and cyanosis of the left foot. She reports being hypertensive and hypothyroid, without other comorbidities, without addictions, without a previous history of lameness or pain in the lower limbs.

Upon admission, there was no evidence of palpable pulses in the left lower limb, with no arterial flow using a portable Doppler flowmeter, with venous flow present. He had toe cyanosis, coldness gradient up to middle third of the leg, with prolonged filling time (4-

5 seconds), preserved mobility and decreased sensitivity in toes. The contralateral lower limb had full and palpable pulses, without cyanosis or coldness. Diagnosis of acute arterial occlusion of the left lower limb with Rutherford classification 2A.

She underwent emergency Duplex Scan of the left lower limb, with a finding of high resistance flow in the proximal segment of the left common iliac and occlusion of the distal segment of the common iliac artery, external iliac artery and common femoral artery, with an image suggestive of the thrombosis, findings these corroborated for the previous diagnostic hypothesis. The patient underwent urgent arterial embolectomy of the left lower limb 12 hours after the onset of symptoms. At the end of the procedure, reestablishment of arterial flow was evidenced, with palpable anterior and posterior femoral, popliteal and tibial pulses, with significant improvement in perfusion, absence of edema and without signs of compartmental limb syndrome.

Patient evolves with resolution of the condition, without complaints. Maintained in a hospitalization regime, during which she performed an echo Doppler cardiogram without evidence of significant intracavitary thrombi or valvopathy. Anticoagulation started with sodium warfarin associated with low molecular weight heparin (LMWH) in an intermediate dose with daily coagulogram control, until reaching the target therapeutic range (INR 2-3). He is discharged 96 hours after admission, suspended LMWH and prescribed warfarin sodium for daily use. Patient currently under outpatient follow-up for INR control. She remains asymptomatic, with preserved physical examination with daily coagulogram control, until reaching the target therapeutic range (INR 2-3). He is discharged 96 hours after admission, suspended LMWH and prescribed warfarin sodium for daily use. Patient currently under outpatient follow-up for INR control. She remains asymptomatic, with preserved physical examination.

Discussion

The present report presents another challenge for Gama variant in cases of acute arterial insufficiency, where the time for limb revascularization is the limiting factor. The delay in referring the patient to the specialized center, the availability of an immediate surgical center is one of the great challenges that vascular surgeons face. We had six patients with acute iliac aorta occlusion and one of them took a long time to be referred and when the limb arrived, they were already unviable and the option was immediate amputation.

The hypothesis as to the cause of this thrombotic event challenges vascular surgeons in the. We had six patients with acute iliac aorta occlusion and one of them took a long time to be referred and when the limb arrived, they were already unviable, and the option was immediate amputation.

The normal interference associated with hypercoagulability or endothelial injury does not explain all cases of thrombosis that occurred in these patients. Immunothrombosis is a more recent concept of association of the thrombotic event associated with infectious and inflammatory and immunological processes. The pro thrombotic imbalance can lead to an increase in the

incidence of micro and macro thrombi as we are observing in these patients.

The two sites that vascular surgeons and hematologists seek to interfere with are platelets and the coagulation cascade, but they are associated with complications such as bleeding. Research shows that prophylactic dosages have protective results like therapeutic dosages, so a number of details must be evaluated when anticoagulation is indicated. Aspirin is another option that has been shown to reduce severity when administered effectively. However, immunothrombosis poses a challenge and what is the best option.^{9,10} None of these behaviors mentioned in isolation are as effective in relation to non-COVID-19 patients.

Therefore, we have observed a failure in anticoagulation. The option we are taking is to associate low-dose aspirin with a prophylactic dose of anticoagulation, the same that we take to prevent recurrent abortions in anticardiolipin and other antiphospholipid antibodies syndrome.¹⁰ We detected in a follow-up study of patients who had venous thrombosis with higher titers that had a higher incidence of new venous thrombosis compared to low titers.^{9,10} A high prevalence of antiphospholipid antibodies has been detected in patients with SARS-CoV-2. However, in the present study we are evaluating an arterial patient, and the management would be the same as that of a venous patient. The present study shows that earlier surgical intervention is indicated, and antithrombotic prevention is necessary.

Conclusion

Arterial thrombosis of large arteries is a logistical challenge in the efficacy of the procedure and the prevention of thrombosis is the author of a challenge where immunothrombosis has warned of a failure in prophylaxis.

Conflict Interest and financial support

The authors declared no have financial support and conflict interest.

Author's contribution

Design and conduct of the study: Da Silva MOM, Santos HA, Godoy HJP, Godoy JMP

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All authors agree the manuscript.

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